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Abstract: The paper shows a number of important e-banking innovations that take place on Polish market. It also presents digital channels trends in e-banking and mobile banking with projections for next five years. All innovations being developed are more and more considered by the banks as an element of their strategy, in order to offer enhanced customer experience and better ménage relations with their customers. A visible trend is integration of digital channels with physical ones. Banks tend to invest more in innovations in order to gain competitive advantage.

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Introduction

Electronic banking is currently recognised among banks as a contemporary direction of banking systems development (Chojecki and Matysek, 2003). Electronic banking is a natural candidate for innovations within the area. In general terms innovation is related with following few aspects. Firstly, it is an introduction of a new product or product species with which consumers have not yet had to deal with. Secondly, it is an introduction of new methods of production, not yet practically proven in the new fields of industry. Next, it may be considered as opening of a new market, i.e. one in which the type of the domestic industry previously did not work, and this regardless of whether the market has existed before or not. Fourthly, it may allow to acquire new sources of raw materials or semi-finished products, regardless of whether the source has already existed or was to be created. And last, it can be understood as an introduction of a new organization industry, such as creation of a monopoly or its breach. (Schumpeter, 1960).

Financial innovations are divided into 3 categories (CASE, BRE Bank, 2005). First category is products and services - offering not existing earlier products, or new channels or new distributions systems. Second one is process - new types for processes. Third one is organisational - new organisational forms.

Within the field of electronic banking the innovations are commonly present in a form of new products of services, as well as new techniques, distribution systems or new electronic banking platforms.

Innovations in the area of electronic banking tend to change rapidly, rather than change existing solutions on the market.

According to a recent research, innovations in banks are becoming more and more popular (EFMA, Infosys/Finacle, 2013). EFMA organisation surveyed 100 banks, where 63% banks declared to be more innovative and 68% of banks are investing more into innovations. Number of banks with innovation strategy grew from 35% in 2009 to 60% in 2013. Simultaneously banks point out several barriers to innovation. IT systems are perceived to be the most significant innovation barrier for banks. The problem with silo-based IT systems is mainly that they increase time to market and the cost of innovation. Other barriers are: regulation, organisation silos, culture, financial, senior management priorities. One of the banks surveyed while pointing out barriers to innovation stressed out more organisational and people factors, where problems were (BNP Paribas, 2013): fear of consequence of failure (the blame culture), people working in narrow boxes, low curiosity, no questioning, poor collaboration, low level of listening and observe approach, reluctance to abandon an old successful product or process.

Digital channels trends

Rapid growth of electronic channels in last decade was strongly visible and significant in retail banking, it impacted the way how the banks operate. Foundations for this is growth of Internet access and proliferation of mobile devices. It is very hard to find a bank without Internet banking offering, in very near future (next couple of years) it would be hard to find a bank without mobile banking.

CHART 1. BANKS VISIONS OF ONLINE AND MOBILE BANKING PROPOSITION IN NEXT FIVE YEARS (%)

Source: EFMA, Kurt Salmon, 2013. "Physical and other digital channels for retail banks", EFMA study, July, www.efma.com, p. 28.

According to recent studies retail banks show tendency of considering digital channels as primary channel for attracting new customers, 63% of surveyed banks take this approach (EFMA, Kurt Salmon, 2013). Customers still tend to be more attached to contact with advisor in terms of buying more complex banking products (see chart 1.). Digital channels continue to be used

for transactions and as complementary channel to branches. The trend is following: bankers believe that the best online tool to generate sales is to drive customers to the branch. Traditional branches and brick-and-mortar stores still generate 90% of sales. Now the trend is to use more omni-channel approach and integrate digital channels also in branch in order to offer enhanced customer experience. Within digital channels human touch is missing, so in response banks are using in Internet banking more and more following tools: online appointment booking, web simulations, request for contact form online (click to call), live web meeting, web chats, secure emails. Above tools are starting to be heavily used to generate leads and sales, banks believe that the most effective is online branch appointment booking (see chart 2.).

CHART 2. BANKS VISIONS ON EFFECTIVENESS OF ONLINE TOOLS IN GENERATING LEADS AND SALES

Source: EFMA, Kurt Salmon, 2013. "Physical and other digital channels for retail banks", EFMA study, July, www.efma.com, p. 29.

CHART 3. DIGITAL SALES TRENDS IN EUROPE

Source: EFMA, 2013. "Retail financial services - strategic insight and best practices", EFMA report, July, www.efma.com, p. 29.

Across Europe there are markets where digital banking is more popular for products purchasing (Scandinavia countries, Western Europe), and countries with less digital banking popularity (south Europe - mainly due to higher saturation of branch network). On chart 3 we can compare e-commerce versus digital sales of banking products.

Recent innovations in electronic banking

Below are presented several innovations that are available on Polish market. Some of them are not yet present in other regions and countries.

Account opening fully online via verification transfer from the other bank

Since 2012 banks in Poland started to offer a possibility of full online account opening process without visit in branch or courier visit. The idea is that the customer verification is based on data placed on the incoming transfer data form the other bank that given customer has. This process can be accomplished in following steps:

- Customer filling in an application to open an account on the website of the bank chooses to confirm the agreement via the other bank transfer's data and provide others bank's account number from which the transfer will be made in order to confirm the opening of the account
- Customer makes a transfer from an account in another bank
- In the case of positive verification (compare the data in the application with the information on the transfer), the transfer is made to return the customer's account in another bank, and the account becomes active
- The customer receives an e-mail or SMS a personalized agreement and instructions on how to login to Internet Banking of given bank.

This year more and more banks are launching the feature such as: Alior, Alior Sync, Multibank, mbank, Meritum, BOS, FM Bank, BGŻ, ING, Nordea, Bank Pocztowy. The popularity of this distribution channel depends on the institution. In BRE Group (mbank and multibank is a 10% the entire acquisition (which is about 140 thousand accounts per year), in Alior Sync - 80 % (at 135 thousand), while in the Meritum Bank in this way are sold 9 out of 10 accounts (bank24.blox.pl, 2013).

Personal finance management

From 2012 more and more banks started to offer PFM solutions, so called personal finance managers. Currently following banks offer the solution to their customers: ING, Millennium, BPH, Meritum, mbank, Alior Sync. Only one these banks offer this on the mobile banking app (Bank Millennium) via internet banking. The first steps of this initiative were taken in the United States, after a decade it also reached also Poland.

The characteristics of the solution depend on the bank, all of them they try to automatically categorise the transactions from the cards and accounts, in some cases there is a possibility to import transaction history from the other

banks. Some of those banks offer just an analysis of income and expenses, some of them allow to create budgets based on historical data of customer's spending and their monitor execution with various notifications. For some transactions like ATM withdrawals there is a possibility to split transactions into several adequate categories. Another feature is that spending habits can be anonymously compared with those of other people with a similar profile. There is a possibility to allocate each expense to member of given household. Recently banks in Poland draw attention to one important aspect of finance management systems, which is to encourage customer to set financial "life goals" (such as "Save for a trip" or "Reduce debt") and map a course to reach them.

The mechanism of expenses and income categorisation is based in terms of card transaction on merchant category code associated with each shop transaction. Some banks also use automatic DDA account categorisation, which can be based on transaction description, sender and receiver account number, receiver or sender names. In most of the cases mechanism is fully online, means that on the moment of transaction it's also automatically categorised, especially cards transaction during authorisation by payments institution.

Major benefits of the PFM for retail banks include:

- Customer Insights and Cross-selling: PFM usage says a lot about customers' financial behaviour. More time spent online also leads to higher conversion
- Brand Building: In a nutshell, PFM is what many of customers want
- Retention: In a time when loyalty is on the decline, PFM is proven to dramatically improve retention
- More Business: PFM users have been shown to be more profitable and tend to increase their business with the bank
- Engagement: More and more people prefer never to visit branches. PFM is a major new channel to engage with customers and earn their trust
- Acquisition: PFM can be a powerful acquisition tool, especially when bundled with other offerings (such as credit cards).

Video conferencing

Banks in Poland started to implement for their customer video conferencing services in online banking solution recently in 2012 (Alior Sync launch) and in 2013 (new reinvented mbank launch). The main purpose of those applications is related with assuring the human touch for digital channels in term of complex products such as mortgage or investments products advise. Service delivered by Alior has desktop and document sharing capabilities (alior.pl, 2013). Thanks to the service it's not necessary to go branch which is located in some kilometres distance from customer place. The problem with videoconferencing on branch level is that requires a lot of Internet bandwidth, which is substantial cost for the banks. On the other hand customers are not

yet that capable and willing to use such service. Chat online features tend to be more popular instead of videoconferencing.

Happy hours

Bank Millennium, one of the banks in Poland, started using a concept of happy hour promotion two years ago on the deposit product, what allows the bank to: stimulate digital sales, cross sell other products digitally for customers that used to check their balances on web, communicate customers via Internet banking.

Happy hours are announced every week. While the happy hours days, announcement is circulated to customers in the morning about the promotion. Offer is personalised in terms of: interest rate (eg. +1%, +2%), time of the deposits (from 1 day up to 732 days) and number of hours of the promotion (bankmillennium.pl, 2013). Usually promotion last few hours. What is interesting is the fact that specific day of the week when promotion is going to happen is not announced in advance, customers need to check it what drives the customer' activity.

What is also unique is the fact that the promotion is also accessible via mobile banking in mobile banking apps. Customers can use the promotion even while being out of the computer access.

Auctions of term deposits

Auctions of term deposits also in Bank Millennium continues to offered after several years. Product is unique on Polish market, no other bank in Poland has this kind of product. In several article journalists emphasize that there is something unique in Polish market in terms of deposits these are - auctions of term deposits by Bank Millennium (bankier.pl, 2013). Auctions are fully integrated with central system of the bank where deposits accounts are stored. Customers are able to place their interest rate bids for given auction of term deposit. Bank defines maximum bid interest rate and maximum pool (volume of deposits based on bids). After all bids are placed bids are sorted by interest rates and time of placing the bid. Winning bids have to be within maximum pool defined by the bank. If the pool is exceeded winning bids are bids with the lowest interest rate and bids that are the earliest (time of placing the bid while bidding period). Each time bank also announces what was the maximum winning bid, and what was average interest rate while given auction.

Payments to email or via Facebook account

Few banks in Poland (Alior Bank, Getin Bank) allow make money transfers without remembering the account number, email, phone number or face book account user name is enough. In internet banking or mobile banking while banking transfers customer is asked for beneficiary email address or phone number or face book account user name. Later the beneficiary has to finish the transfer on special page beneficiary has to provide his account number in order

to receive the money. On face book it can be account number inserted to personal information file, so the next transfers do not require it.

Prepaid card with unique features

Since December 2012 Bank Millennium has been offering an innovative prepaid card for its customers (prnews.pl, 2013). The Millennium MasterCard Prepaid is a card, which can be opened in a complete online process, without a need to visit bank's branch. The card can be issued to a child or to any other person aged 13+. Both card owner (a person who ordered a card) and card user (a person who uses the card) can manage and control the card with a variety of channels, such as Internet banking, mobile banking as well as telephone and SMS services.

Apart from standard benefits of prepaid cards, such as convenience and safety, Millennium Bank's MasterCard Prepaid card is equipped with many attractive features, which makes it the most innovative card in Poland. Card can be used by parents as a way to give electronic pocket money to their kids. Not only a parent has control over daily transaction limits (POS and ATM), but can also see a full transaction history of kid's card, including in-depth analysis of spending with the use of Personal Finance Manager. Parent can also set SMS notifications in order to be informed about all transactions made by the child and can check the balance on a card with SMS inquiry in any given moment. Having a separate access to Bank's internet banking application, a child can see all the necessary information about the card such as available balance, transaction history or daily limits. Child can also use the Personal Finance Manager, which is a great tool for learning how to manage and control finances. Another feature of prepaid cards in Bank Millennium is the possibility of sharing card's account number with friends on Facebook, which makes the process much easier and faster than sending account number in a regular way.

Millennium's prepaid card can be also used a special purpose card, for example for travelling abroad or for online payments, since it offers the highest safety level thanks to the 3D-Secure service and insurance packages embedded to it. Alternatively it also can be used as gift card (different occasions - birthday, Christmas, etc.).

Mobile payments without card

The biggest banks on the Polish market (PKO BP, BRE, ING, Millennium, BZWBK, Alior) are planning to launch mobile payments standard in Poland. After the standard is launched all the remaining banks and other parties can join the standard. The joint venture was announced in 2013 based on solution form PKO BP called IKO which mobile banking apps that allows for (pkobp.pl, 2013):

- Making payments in traditional stores
- Withdrawals from ATMs without a card
- Transferring money to a phone number without the need to enter an account number

- Making payments online stores by using "pay with IKO"
- Generating checks allow paying in shops or withdrawing money from ATMs without a phone
- Finding the nearest points and ATM transactions taking IKO
- Checking balances and account transaction history plugged to support applications.

NFC

In October 2012 first Polish operator T-mobile with two banks (Polbank and mbank) under auspices of Mastercard and with use of Casis, Gemalto (Trusted Service Managers providers) launched the biggest NFC payment project live for customer. It is also one of the biggest projects worldwide. The innovative project on Polish market enables for customers to perform contactless payments via mobile phones, where payment instrument ("virtual card") is located automatically on handset's SIM card. The communication between payment instrument provider (bank) and MNO operator is provided thanks to Trusted Service Manager that allows for over the air (OTA) instrument personalisation for given customer.

For customers this kind of payment is very convenient, mobile device is enough to perform payments in traditional stores with contactless terminals, where by one tap payment can be performed.

Barriers related with NFC development are not IT based, but business model based, where banks are not interested to pay 4 or 5 times more than standard physical personalised payment card. Secondly there are some limitations in terms of devices where payment instrument can be stored they have to be NFC complaint and have to have special SIM card. Another barrier to NFC is a number of contactless terminals, which is in fact in Poland quite advanced compared to other countries.

Bills payments with usage QR codes

Bills, invoices or any other payment documents equipped payment information on the QR code can be paid via innovative service available on mobile banking apps. The feature allows it to read payment data via usage QR code scanner inside mobile app and after to present the payment data onto transfer form and make a payment via mobile banking. The service allows to quickly perform bill payment with much typing on the phone. Both paper and electronic bills can be scanned. This feature is unique on Polish market, only few banks have it, gaining more popularity.

Conclusion

Electronic banking in Poland has many innovative products and services that are unique on Polish market, not yet present in the other countries. Innovation is a key trend, but sometimes it is getting mixed reviews in terms of

effectiveness and requires much greater focus. Some of the innovations like videoconferencing or mobile payments are the early adopting stage due to several limitations mentioned above.

Innovative products are more and more moving from Internet into Mobile. Generation Y that is entering the mobile banking services or even younger people are accustomed to remote contact, it is their natural form for contacting the bank. Electronic banking channels are becoming more and more contact point where their issues can be solved from A to Z, without visiting the branch, that is why development of digital innovation is very important. There is also a visible trend of integrating digital channels with physical ones.

Banks more and more realise that innovation strategy is key in keeping the relationship with customers, being up to date with recent trends. Banks tend to invest more in innovations and have it as a strategy. The key challenge are often IT systems, which can hinder innovation, at least partly due to product and channel silos.

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